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IWT Bremen

Additive Manufactured Metallic Force Transmissions in Fibre Reinforced Thermoplastics

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Joining technologies

State of the art

Metal/FRP:
riveting

Source: [Fran12]

adhesives

Source: Henkel

inserts

Source: J. Fleischer et al., Lightweight Design, Ed. 2012-05

FDS screws

Source: Böllhoff

Metal/metal:

Further...

...prevalent in automotive industry:

Spot welding

How to combine?

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Large scale specimen

Design of coupon

Experimental setup

Bottom view

Top view

Design of metal insert

F (shear)

+ Covered with patch

F (shear)

Notches and surface

Notches and holes

T-shape

Optimisation goals

- Input: material data and boundary conditions
- Introduction of force: adhesive forces and tight fit \uparrow
- Transmission of force: uniform stress distribution in insert \uparrow

Adhesion – lap shear

Surface topographie

Topographie depending on surface treatment influencing adhesion force

None:

[Max.: 52 μm ; Min.: 41 μm]

Sandblasted:

[Max.: 34 μm ; Min.: 36 μm]

Plasma- and gas-nitrided:

[Max.: 65 μm ; Min.: 35 μm]

Red: high
Blue: low

DLC-coated:

[Max.: 49 μm ; Min.: 42 μm]

Corroded:

[Max.: 67 μm ; Min.: 53 μm]

Slide grinded:

[Max.: 51 μm ; Min.: 42 μm]

Measuring Range:
1350 μm x 1012 μm

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Exemplary designs

Full body

Design with 5 arms

Design with 3 arms

Detail round edges

Stress distribution

Failure modes

1. Welding spot

2. Adhesion/form fit

3. Intermediate Insert/adhesion

4. Insert

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Thank you!

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